

Actual vs Predicted (SunHoursMin)

Standardized Residuals (SunHoursMin)

Partial Regression Plot (SunHoursMin)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.2664$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 3.3116

p-value: 0.0688

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 3.9695

df: 2

p-value: 0.1374

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (SunHoursMin)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – SunHoursMin

